

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF THE CVIF-DLP-APPROACH IN ONE SHS STEM CLASS ACROSS FIVE COURSES

Dr. Marlowe Louis F. Fabunan ¹
Dr. Archieval A. Rodriguez ²

¹ *School of Education, Arellano University-Jose Abad Santos Campus, Pasay City, Philippines*

² *Ilaya Barangka Integrated School, Mandaluyong City, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10770463>

ABSTRACT

Innovative educational programs play a significant role in shaping the academic landscape to enhance teaching and learning quality. The Bernido couple's pioneering efforts have led to the development of the Central Visayan Institute Foundation-Dynamic Learning Program (CVIF-DLP), which has been embraced by institutions like Arellano University. At Arellano University, the Bernido couple introduced and implemented the CVIF-DLP curriculum, providing students with the autonomy to construct their own learning experiences. The implementation of CVIF-DLP at Arellano University began in 2009 after the Bernido couple trained the faculty on its principles and methodologies across the elementary and high school departments. This study aims to investigate the potential impact of the CVIF-DLP Approach on the teaching and learning of key subjects including Statistics, Calculus, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics among grade 10 students at Arellano University. Employing an Ex-post facto research design, this study examines the academic performance of a STEM class at AU-SHS across these five courses. This design enables the exploration of relationships between the independent variable (CVIF-DLP implementation) and the dependent variable (academic achievement) without direct intervention. The study's findings reveal a homogeneous distribution of scores across all five courses. It suggests the need for customization of the DLP-approach to cater to the unique demands of each subject. It advocates for the adaptation of teaching strategies, resources, and assessments to address the specific requirements of Physics, Biology, Chemistry, Calculus, and Statistics. Furthermore, the study recommends further research to delve into specific aspects of the CVIF-DLP teaching approach, such as its impact on

students' ability to assume ownership of their learning and the dynamics between teachers of different subjects under the CVIF-DLP framework.

Keywords: *CVIF-DLP Approach, academic achievement, learning, STEM*

INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of enhancing the quality of teaching and learning, educational programs that embrace innovation play a pivotal role in shaping the academic landscape. One such initiative, known as the Central Visayan Institute Foundation-Dynamic Learning Program (CVIF-DLP) Dynamic), has been introduced in the Central Visayas by the visionary efforts of the Bernido couple.

The Central Visayan Institute Foundation-Dynamic Learning Program (CVIF-DLP) pioneered by Christopher C. Bernido and Maria Victoria Bernido, stands as a testament to the commitment to revolutionize education. This program is designed to cultivate a dynamic, learner-centered environment, fostering active student engagement and critical thinking skills. As this innovative approach gains momentum in Central Visayas, it is essential to evaluate its impact on diverse academic disciplines. The Dynamic Learning Program is based on the premise of "learning by doing," it is student-centered, and it is a teaching approach that emphasizes student action rather than typical classroom lectures. Students study independently in this program since each activity has a clear learning goal. According to (Marpa, 2016), DLP is a teaching system that focuses on students' activities rather than typical classroom lectures, where pupils learn individually because activities are offered with clear and precise learning outcomes.

Arellano University is one of the well-known universities that has implemented the Dynamic Learning Program (DLP), a revolutionary learning approach. The Bernido couple recommended this concept for adoption at Arellano University. The learner must have the freedom to develop his or her own learning in this strategy. The learner's prior experience is critical for transferring new knowledge promptly. Furthermore, the learner must be willing to learn. The learners' orientation is crucial; that is, this method is student centered rather than subject oriented (Gambayan, 2014). According to the study of Delos Reyes, R.D.G (2020), the finding resulted in several mitigating factors, including the teaching technique itself and a good guidance program. More research on the CVIF-DLP teaching strategy, its effect on learner autonomy, and a full description of the rapport among specific topic teachers are recommended for a more in-depth understanding.

The STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) curriculum is renowned for its emphasis on rigorous academic content and practical application of knowledge. As educational institutions strive to prepare students for the demands of the 21st century, the integration of innovative teaching methods becomes imperative. In the study of Bernido, C.C., Bernido, M.V. (2020), the challenges of providing quality education for the general population, in the arts and social sciences, and especially in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM), remain difficult.

Thus, the researchers attempt to uncover the potential effects of the DLP Approach in the teaching and learning of Statistics, Calculus, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics by grade 10 students at Arellano University, which began implementing DLP in the

elementary and high school departments in 2009 after the Bernido couple oriented and trained the faculty on how it should be implemented. Since then, only Gambayan has conducted research that has demonstrated its efficiency in the teaching and learning of reading by Grade 10 students.

Through this research, the researchers aspire to contribute to the continual enhancement of educational practices and student learning experiences in the STEM field.

Research Questions

To give light to the problem, the researchers sought answers to the following questions:

1. What will be the description of one AU SHS-STEM class in:
 - 1.1. Statistics,
 - 1.2. Calculus,
 - 1.3. Physics,
 - 1.4. Biology and
 - 1.5. Chemistry?
2. Will there be a significant difference from:
 - 2.1. Statistics to Calculus,
 - 2.2. Calculus to Physics and
 - 2.3. Biology to Chemistry?
3. Will there be a significant relationship from:
 - 3.1. Biology to Chemistry,
 - 3.2. Biology to Physics,
 - 3.3. Calculus to Physics and
 - 3.4. Chemistry to Physics?

METHODOLOGY

This study employs an Ex-post facto research design to examine the academic achievement of the Dynamic Learning Program (DLP)-Approach in one AU-SHS STEM class across five courses. The use of this design allows for the exploration of relationships between the independent variable (implementation of the DLP-Approach) and the dependent variable (academic achievement) without direct manipulation.

The participants will consist of students enrolled in the specified AU-SHS STEM class Academic Year 2021-2022. The sample size will be determined based on the availability of data and the number of students present in the selected courses. Cumulative academic records, including grades, scores, and assessments, will be collected for each student across the specified course.

Descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, will be computed to describe academic achievement. Inferential statistics, such as ANOVA or t-tests, will be applied to identify any significant differences between groups.

Informed consent will be obtained from participants, ensuring they are fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Participants confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained throughout the study.

The study's retrospective nature may limit the control over confounding variables. Causality cannot be established due to the Ex-post facto design.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Physics		Biology		Calculus		Chemistry		Statistics	
Mean	19.58	Mean	16.8	Mean	12.44	Mean	16.7	Mean	18.86

Table 1 reveals that means of all the five courses have a verbal interpretation of poor performance. The verbal interpretation of "poor performance" suggests that, on average, students in all five courses have achieved scores that are considered below a satisfactory or acceptable level. The collective average performance across all courses is indicating a need for improvement. It suggests that, as a group, students are facing challenges in achieving higher scores in their respective courses. While the overall mean suggests poor performance, it would be valuable to examine individual course means to identify specific areas of concern.

Table 2

Score Range	Physics	Biology	Calculus	Chemistry	Statistics	Description
41-50						Outstanding
31-40	3					Very good
21-30	21	8	1	7	17	Good
11-20	22	39	34	41	32	Poor
1-10	4	3	15	2	1	Very Poor
0						No Learning
Total	50	50	50	50	50	

Table 2 shows the frequency distribution of scores of the five courses. It provides a breakdown of the scores achieved by students in each of the five courses.

Table 3

Table 3 shows that the homogeneity of the STEM students in Statistics course is classified as poor students. The classification as "Poor" indicates that there is a notable lack of uniformity or consistency in the students' performance in the Statistics course. This classification prompts teachers and administrators to explore strategies for improving overall understanding and achievement in Statistics within this specific group of students.

Table 4

Table 4 shows that the homogeneity of the STEM 6 in Calculus course is classified as poor students. This indicates that the group of students in STEM 6, specifically in the Calculus course, demonstrates a notable lack of uniformity or similarity in their performance. The students in STEM 6 exhibit diverse levels of understanding or proficiency in Calculus. There is significant spread of scores, with some students performing well while others struggle in the Calculus course. This suggests a potential need for targeted interventions or instructional adjustments to address the varying levels of preparedness or grasp of the subject matter.

Table 5

Table 5 shows the homogeneity that the STEM 6 in Physics course is classified as between good and poor students. The students exhibit a mix of proficiency levels in the Physics course, with some performing at a good level and others at a lower, potentially poor level.

This classification implies a moderate need for targeted interventions or instructional adjustments to address the varying levels of preparedness or understanding within the group.

Table 6

Table 6 shows the homogeneity that the STEM 6 in Biology course is classified as between good and poor students. The classification as "between good and poor" indicates a moderate level of diversity or variability in the students' performance in the Biology course. Some students may be performing well, while others may be struggling to a certain extent. The students in STEM 6 exhibit a mix of proficiency levels in the Biology course, with some performing at a good level and others at a lower, potentially poor level. This classification suggests a moderate need for targeted interventions or instructional adjustments to address the varying levels of preparedness or understanding within the group.

Table 7

Table 7 shows the homogeneity that the STEM 6 in Chemistry course is classified as between good and poor students. The classification as "between good and poor" suggests a moderate level of diversity or variability in the students' performance in the Chemistry course. Some students may be performing well, while others may be struggling to a certain extent.

Table 8

Subjects to be compared	P Value	Level of Significance	Interpretation	Decision
Statistics and Calculus	7.67 E-12	0.05	Significant	Reject the Ho
Calculus and Physics	3.99 E-21	0.05	Significant	Reject the Ho
Biology and Chemistry	0.87	0.05	Not Significant	Accept the Ho

Table 8 shows the comparison of Statistics and Calculus had P value of 7.67E-12 which is interpreted as reject the Ho, while Calculus and Physics had a P value of 3.99E-21 which is interpreted as reject the Ho, and lastly Biology to Chemistry had a P value of 0.87 which is interpreted as accept the Ho.

The Statistics and Calculus groups and the Calculus and Physics groups show statistically significant differences based on the extremely small p-values, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

On the other hand, the Biology and Chemistry groups do not show statistically significant differences, as indicated by the larger p-value, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 9

Subjects to be correlated	R	Description	P value	Level of Significance	Interpretation	Decision
Biology to Chemistry	0.31	Moderately Weak Positive	0.027	0.05	Significant	Reject the Ho
Biology to Physics	0.43	Moderately Weak Positive	0.43	0.05	Not Significant	Accept the Ho
Calculus to Physics	0.23	Weak Positive	0.10	0.05	Not Significant	Accept the Ho
Chemistry to Physics	0.27	Weak Positive	0.050	0.05	Significant	Reject the Ho

Table 9 show that the relationship between Biology to Chemistry had a value of r 0.31 with a description of moderately weak positive and got the P value of 0.027 which interpreted as reject the Ho. While between Biology to Physics had a value of r 0.43 with a description of Moderately weak positive and go the P value of 0.43 which interpreted as accept the Ho. While between Calculus to Physics had a value of r 0.23 with a description of weak positive and go the P value of 0.10 which interpreted as accept the Ho, and lastly between Chemistry to Physics had a value of r 0.27 with a description of weak positive and go the P value of 0.05 which interpreted as reject the Ho.

There is evidence of a statistically significant, moderately weak positive correlation between Biology and Chemistry, as well as between Chemistry and Physics.

There is no statistically significant correlation between Biology and Physics or between Calculus and Physics based on the given p-values.

The correlation coefficient values indicate the strength and direction of the relationships, with all described as weak to moderately weak positive correlations.

It is consistent to the study of Delos Reyes, R.D.G (2020), the finding resulted in several mitigating factors, including the teaching technique itself and a good guidance program. More research on the CVIF-DLP teaching strategy, its effect on learner autonomy, and a full description of the rapport among specific topic teachers are recommended for a more in-depth understanding. The use of DLP should be given more attention, but teachers should also be encouraged to change their techniques because the appropriateness of the approach to be utilized in a particular topic is highly crucial. (Marpa, 2016). Based on the findings of the study of Basilio (2009), there is no significant difference in the posttests scores of students with no experience of the DLP and those who are exposed to it.

Conclusions

1. As impoverished students, the means and frequency distribution of the scores for all five courses are homogeneous. There may be various elements to consider and choose from when categorizing individual learning styles.
2. When comparing courses, the researchers discover three patterns: math versus math, math versus science, and science versus science. The courses Statistics and Calculus, which had a verbal meaning of significant, followed the pattern from math to math. The researchers discover that Calculus is a higher form of mathematical concepts that distinguishes Statistics from Calculus. The second pattern demonstrates that Calculus and Physics differ significantly in that Physics can be viewed in a traditional approach that does not require prior knowledge in Calculus. The third pattern demonstrates that there is no significant distinction between Biology and Chemistry because some concepts in the two courses differ even though they belong to the same discipline of study.
3. The significance of the interaction between biology and chemistry explains why students obtain correlational learning between biology and chemistry. As a result, the difference between Biology and Physics is insignificant because most of the concepts are unrelated. While Calculus to Physics is not significant because the teacher may not have used Calculus principles in teaching Physics. Finally, the relationship between Chemistry and Physics is significant because Chemistry concepts can be applied in Physics.

Recommendations

The researchers recommended the following to the AU-SHS STEM class to optimize the benefits of the DLP-Approach and create a learning environment that nurtures curiosity, critical thinking, and interdisciplinary connections across the five courses.

1. Tailor the DLP-Approach to the specific needs and characteristics of each course. Customize instructional strategies, resources, and assessments to align with the unique requirements of Physics, Biology, Chemistry, Calculus, and Statistics.
2. Offer targeted professional development sessions for teachers to enhance their understanding and proficiency in implementing the DLP-Approach across diverse subjects. Focus on subject-specific pedagogy and strategies that align with the principles of dynamic learning.

3. Establish a system for ongoing teacher support, mentorship, and collaborative learning communities. Foster a culture of continuous improvement by providing resources, feedback, and opportunities for shared reflection among educators.
4. Emphasize the integration of real-world applications in each course to enhance students' understanding and appreciation of the relevance of their learning. Design projects and activities that bridge theoretical knowledge with practical, real-life scenarios.
5. Ensure that assessments align with the objectives and learning outcomes of each course under the DLP-Approach. Implement a variety of assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, to capture the diverse aspects of student learning.
6. Establish effective feedback mechanisms for both students and teachers. Encourage a feedback loop where students receive timely and constructive feedback on their performance, and teachers receive feedback on the effectiveness of their instructional methods.
7. Strengthen the integration of technology in the classroom to support the DLP-Approach. Ensure that the necessary technological infrastructure is in place to facilitate the seamless use of multimedia, interactive content, and online resources.
8. Prioritize student-centered learning experiences that empower students to take an active role in their education. Foster a learning environment that encourages inquiry, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving.
9. Promote interdisciplinary collaboration among teachers to enhance the coherence and synergy across the five courses. Encourage joint planning, collaborative projects, and cross-disciplinary discussions.
10. Involve parents/guardians in the educational process. Share insights into the DLP-Approach, its benefits, and how the parents/guardian can support student learning at home.
11. Establish a long-term monitoring and evaluation plan to track the sustained impact of the DLP-Approach on student outcomes. Regularly assess and adjust the approach based on ongoing evaluations.
12. Additional research in specific areas related to the CVIF-DLP teaching approach to explore how this approach impacts students' ability to take charge of their own learning and to understand the interpersonal dynamics among teachers of different subjects under the CVIF-DLP approach. The appropriateness of the teaching method for a specific topic is highlighted as an important consideration, emphasizing the relevance of aligning instructional strategies with the content being taught.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

I, Dr. Marlowe Louis F. Fabunan, and Dr. Archieval A. Rodriguez, thus declare that all information gathered and made available in this study was received with the consent of the respondents. They were appropriately informed and given the option to withdraw from the study at any time. The respondents' anonymity was maintained, they were not subjected to any form of harm, there was no conflict of interest in the study's conduct, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, and the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researchers extend their heartfelt appreciation to all those who have been instrumental in the successful completion of this research project. Their support, guidance, and encouragement have played a significant role in shaping the outcomes of this study.

Above all, to God, the creator of all things. He had given the researchers the gift of knowledge and understanding, which has guided the researchers to this point of fulfilment.

To the faculty members of the School of Education for their constructive feedback and scholarly guidance. Their collective wisdom has enriched the research methodology and contributed to the robustness of the findings.

Special thanks are due to SHS Faculty Members for their support, which has been crucial in the successful execution of this research. Their commitment to fostering academic inquiry has been instrumental in bringing this project to fruition.

Furthermore, the researchers extend their gratitude to their friends and family for their unwavering support, understanding, and encouragement throughout the research journey. Their belief in the abilities of the researchers has been a constant source of motivation.

Finally, deepest appreciation goes to the participants of this study, whose willingness to share their experiences and perspectives has been fundamental to the depth and richness of the findings.

Thank you all for your contributions, support, and encouragement. This research would not have been possible without your collaborative efforts.

REFERENCES

- Basilio, M. G. A. (2009). The adaptation of the Dynamic Learning Program. *ADDU-SAS Graduate School Research Journal*, 5(1),
- Bernido, C.C., Bernido, M.V. (2020). Essentials Over Peripherals: The CVIF Dynamic Learning Program. In: Panth, B., Maclean, R. (eds) *Anticipating and Preparing for Emerging Skills and Jobs. Education in the Asia-Pacific Region: Issues, Concerns and Prospects*, vol 55. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7018-6_9

Delos Reyes, R.D.G., Torio, V.A.G. The Relationship of Expert Teacher–Learner Rapport and Learner Autonomy in the CVIF-Dynamic Learning Program. *Asia-Pacific Edu Res* 30, 471–481 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-020-00532-y>

Gambayan, A. (2016). *Dynamic Learning Program*. Arellano University, Manila.

Marpa, E (2016). Mathematics Teachers’ and Students’ Perceptions on the Implementation of the Dynamic Learning Program (DLP). *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 6, Issue 8, August 2016
